

A CONCEPTUAL STUDY IN UNDERSTANDING THE IMPACT OF IMPLEMENTING ROBOTICS ON BUSINESS MANAGEMENT FOR SUSTAINABLE GROWTH

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Abstract

The digital age is forcing companies to become accustomed to using new and innovative technologies to improve productivity and performance. The use of AI in assisting business processes to achieve the management of various functions including finance, economy, chain management, human resources, economics as costs, generating good revenue, GDP, n.k. The use of AI improves performance and also provides support to achieve growth and development. The researcher used important and secondary data to perform the analysis, approximately 91 responses were received, and these data were analyzed for percentage analysis. The second report comes from various online libraries such as EBSCO and others to gain a better understanding of previous studies in this area.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Management, Economics, Sustainable development

Introduction

Remember that the world is changing rapidly. The emergence of tools such as robotics, automation and intelligence (AI) has made the business process more efficient and cost-effective. Technological advances have made the world a smaller place and companies are looking for key connections with their partners to achieve growth and development (Choi,

2019). The world is changing rapidly. There is no era in history where almost everywhere, be it human, economic or political, has been affected by rapid change through the development of information technology. Advances in technology have made it possible for people to have more energy, to get faster transportation to transport people, goods and services, to improve communication speed, to send the same people to the moon and even to work in space. Duty to the sun. Technology has enabled people to better diagnose and treat disease. This is evidenced by the speed at which the COVID-19 dose was developed and used to combat infections that will occur worldwide in the first quarter of 2020 (Tankiso, 2020).

Artificial intelligence is a tool used to create mathematical intelligence. There are three types of mental skills: machine learning, computer skills, and basic arithmetic. Intelligence is the use of intelligence tools, such as groups of birds or insects, to create intelligent machines. Chinese intelligence has been used successfully to create systems like Google Maps that determine the smallest of the two dots. (Luís Language 2020). The "digital age" began with the use of the internet and mobile phones, when companies opened their online stores to interact with their customers, forcing governments to accept them, the internet government and financial institutions. On tablets, mobile phones and social networks. Major changes that have taken place in the development of new businesses called e-commerce include e-signing, e-invoicing, e-commerce, internet, mobile banking and electronic payments, creating use in the lives of companies and individuals. . Reducing or simplifying operations, reshaping business processes for the online business environment has transformed the business era into a digital era. On the other hand, the development of a data error business environment to analyze big data when working with CRM systems.

Although the digital age is intertwined with other disciplines such as technology, nanotechnology, genetics and so on. (Chopra 2019). In short, it is a step towards "aerospace economy", another direct or indirect growth of companies and economies on other developments. These improvements are called robotics and artificial intelligence. The "Industrial Age" began with the Industrial Revolution and mechanization, especially in the UK by car manufacturers. The production and sale of valuable goods had a profound effect on industry and commerce in the early 20th century. H. Capital, economy, employment, land are all affected by the improvement of the industrial age and technology, and life, education, finance and agriculture are also affected by these effects. To address new issues and issues, staff and supervisors have developed the need for higher education through grade data, decision-making and efficiency. To work simultaneously in manufacturing facilities or production channels, workers began in apartment buildings, supermarkets or buildings with a focus on urban life rather than city. Wages and wealth have changed the attitudes of businessmen and people (Wong, 2020)

Literature review

As the mind grasps all aspects of human life, human thoughts and actions are fundamentally changing. In general, people rely on business and financial assumptions to understand concepts such as quality comparisons, long-term business growth, lack or data inequality, and the role

of failure is critical in designing and making decisions. Procedures for allocating resources between different perspectives (Wirth, 2018).

The most important of these theories is that they try to eliminate the effects of uncertainty by trying to recapture the future for the present. The principles in this section are rooted in risk management and risk management. The 31000 International Organization for Standardization (ISO) standard defines risk as "the result of objective uncertainty". In other words, uncertainty is a significant difference in expected outcomes.

In practice, business-oriented research has always provided a good basis for misunderstandings and the importance of decision-making. The market has made this happen through a variety of models that are trying to predict the future. Risk management, on the other hand, aims to reduce or reduce this uncertainty so that the "software developer" can achieve positive results (Rampersad, 2020).

As discussed earlier, the most important aspect of business theory is that they try to eliminate the effects of uncertainty by trying to reciprocate the present moment. Scientists say that intellectual property (at least in its current state) "does not give us intelligence, but the essence of intelligence: prediction." This has led to the history of human beings developing economic and financial perspectives. As intellectual property rights provide our basic knowledge, it affects how business and financial needs are presented (Rampersad, 2016). This article examines how property can redefine some of the key business and financial issues that have stood the test of time. Representation can make the right decisions. Manufacturing, communications, business and labor costs, as well as finance and investment, including real-time / online impact of value proposals and customer supplies are available on the balance sheet and cargo bills and increase sales and delivery time for robots. Channel distribution can effectively control the pros and cons.

Research methodology

The term research is seen as an important part of research as it helps the scientist to create beautiful designs and use different tools to better understand concepts. The researcher used an in-depth study technique that enabled him to gain a better understanding that researchers used closed questions to record data and information of researchers, noting that using best practices would help research more effectively and efficiently, the purpose of mass training.

Critical Discussion

Based on the overall results, it can be said that AI makes it possible to improve business management and make it more profitable for companies. Artificial intelligence is a tool used to create mathematical intelligence. There are three main types of technical education: machine learning, computer skills, and simple arithmetic. Mathematical intelligence is the use of intelligent biological systems, such as bird groups or ant colonies, in the development of intelligent systems. Chinese intelligence has been used successfully to create systems like Google Maps that determine the smallest of the two dots. The "digital age" that began with the

use of the internet and mobile phones, when companies opened their online stores and online stores to interact with their customers, forced the government to launch its own electronic government, and create financial companies. On tablets, mobile phones and social networks. Major changes that have taken place in the development of new businesses called e-commerce include electronic signature, electronic invoice, online business, internet, mobile banking and electronic payments, electronics, positive and negative savings. By reducing or simplifying operations, redesigning business processes using the online business environment has transformed the business era into a digital era. On the other hand, the development of a data error business environment to analyze big data when working with CRM systems. Although the digital age is close to other sciences like technology, nanotechnology, genetics and so on.

Conclusion

In practice, basic business research has always provided a good foundation for understanding the concepts of uncertainty and determination. The market has made this happen through a variety of models that are trying to predict the future. Risk management, on the other hand, seeks to reduce or reduce this uncertainty so that the "developer" can achieve better results. Applying this experience to business processes helps to control various activities such as finance, manufacturing, chain management, human resources, finance such as revenue, revenue, revenue, GDP, n.k. Using AI will help you better understand the process. And encouraging growth and development achievements...

Future scope

To understand the role of AI in industry and business management, the researcher has been trying to understand the concept of using AI in the affected areas as a whole, to determine who it might be so that research can continue. This will lead to a greater understanding of the role of AI in leadership and the ability to take advantage of various marketing opportunities.

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